

Application of chemiluminescence analysis to evaluate the recyclability of polypropylene

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the degradation and remaining stability of polymers before recycling is crucial for obtaining high-quality recycled materials. This study explores chemiluminescence (CL) analysis as a tool for monitoring the degradation level and oxidative stability of polypropylene (PP) and proposes indicators for assessing the recyclability of polymers. PP samples containing different degradation and stability levels were characterized by CL measurements in air (CL-air) and in nitrogen (CL-N₂). This study demonstrates that the CL-air measurements effectively measure the oxidative stability of PP, providing several stability indicators. Furthermore, it is shown that the degradation levels assessed by CL-air correlate with those from CL-N₂. Hence, it is possible to simultaneously assess the degradation level and the thermal-oxidative stability of PP through a single CL-air measurement, providing essential insights for evaluating the best routes for the recycling of plastics.

1. Introduction

Recycling is considered essential for achieving a plastics circular economy [1–3]. During mechanical recycling, waste plastics are physically converted into new products, ideally preserving the chemical structure of the macromolecules [4]. However, oxidative degradation of polymer chains is commonly observed during melt processing, lifetime, and recycling, and this can prevent high-quality recycling via the mechanical route, as it leads to changes in physicochemical properties [5].

Polypropylene (PP) is a widely used polymer and represents more than 19 % of global plastic production [6]. PP can undergo oxidative degradation during both (re)processing and service life, even with the use of antioxidants (AO), leading to chemical and structural modifications of the polymer chain [7–9]. It is well established in the literature that the degradation of PP is heterogeneous, which results from the presence of catalyst residues that initiate degradation [7,10–13]. Celina and George [12] proposed an infectious spreading model to describe the growth of oxidative degradation, indicating that this spreading occurs from highly reactive sites towards the remaining parts of the material. They concluded that the overall oxidation of PP is controlled by the weakest sites. Consequently, small amounts of degraded material can induce oxidative degradation of unaffected PP fractions during processing, limiting its recyclability [14,15]. This heterogeneous nature and

physical spreading of oxidative degradation pose a significant challenge for the long-term recycling of PP.

The oxidative degradation of polymers is commonly described by the auto-oxidation mechanism proposed by Bolland and Gee [16] (Fig. 1). This mechanism includes four stages: (i) initiation, (ii) propagation, (iii) chain branching, and (iv) termination. Within the initiation reaction, macromolecular radicals are formed. Catalyst residues containing metal ions can be responsible for the heterogeneous radical formation [11,17,18]. The propagation stage involves the reaction of these radicals with oxygen. Regarding PP, the average number of propagation cycles is higher compared to other polymers, like polyethylene [8]. In PP, propagation can occur according to an in-chain reaction, leading to adjacent hydroperoxides [14]. The chain branching reaction involves hydroperoxide decomposition. The decomposition of hydroperoxides forms new radicals that, in turn, promote new propagation reactions, being responsible for the auto-acceleration behavior of oxidative degradation. The termination reaction consists of the bimolecular recombination of radicals.

Several characterization techniques have been used to study the oxidative degradation of polymers. Among these, the lesser-known chemiluminescence (CL) analysis is advantageous due to its high sensitivity compared to other characterization techniques [19]. The oxidation of polymers, including PP, is accompanied by

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chemiluminescence, making it useful for monitoring their oxidative degradation [12,20]. It was previously found that CL detects substantial changes in oxidative stability sooner than the carbonyl index measured by FTIR, or the oxidation induction time (OIT) measured via differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) [10,21]. Mechanical characterization, such as tensile and impact tests, is often used to indirectly study the effects of degradation as a result of repeated processing, but such tests do not determine the actual degradation level [22–24]. The same applies to changes in the melt flow rate (MFR), which can be indicative of degradation [25], but only in a comparative fashion when the polymer's original behaviour is known. Complementary to mechanical characterization, CL provides a more complete and accurate view of polymers' degradation and stability.

During CL analysis in an oxidative atmosphere, the surface of a polymer sample undergoes oxidation. It has been shown that the shape of the CL intensity curve is comparable to the derivative of the oxidation curve [26,27]. Integration of the CL curve results in an oxidation curve that is similar to an oxygen uptake curve. Therefore, the CL curve measured in an oxidative environment is viewed as a measure of the oxidation rate [28]. Although oxidation cannot happen in an inert environment, it has been shown that polymers still emit light in such an atmosphere [20]. Upon heating polymers in an inert environment such as N₂, the CL signal results in a peak and its area is proportional to the hydroperoxide concentration in the early stages of oxidation; this area is called the total luminescence intensity (TLI) [29].

Polymer degradation by oxidation typically occurs throughout all stages of the material's lifespan, *i.e.*, fabrication, product use, and recycling. As a result, the degradation level of a polymer increases over time. Given the increasing necessity of plastic recycling, it is crucial to consider how the degradation level of plastics and the recycling process affect their potential to be successfully reintroduced as raw materials into a new lifecycle.

To investigate the mechanical recycling on a lab scale, recycling is often simulated by consecutive cycles of extrusion and granulation [22]. Such a method is valuable for developing strategies for the reprocessing of polymers, but it does not include a representation of the lifespan of a product, nor the complexity of waste management. A lab scale method that more closely resembles recycling consists of applying multiple cycles of alternating accelerated aging and reprocessing by extrusion [21, 30]. The latter has been used to show that the oxidation products generated during accelerated aging intensify the degradation during extrusion, resulting in earlier failure.

Several studies have used CL to examine the effect of stabilization systems on the thermal-oxidative stability of virgin polymers, showing that the CL signal varies with the type and concentration of stabilizers used [15,26,31–37]. Some authors also examined the stability of polymers subjected to simulated recycling via CL analysis. Notably, Fearon et al. [36] showed that the oxygen induction time (OIT) obtained by CL can be effectively used to assess the impact of antioxidants on PP stability. Moreover, Hamskog et al. [15] used CL-OIT to assess the

efficiency of several stabilization systems during simulated recycling experiments. In another comprehensive study, Hamskog et al. demonstrated that adding extra stabilizers to recycled PP is substantially more effective than preparing blends of virgin and recycled PP [37]. According to Gijman and Fiorio [14], it would be even better to prevent the complete consumption of stabilizers during PP's first lifecycle as this would prevent the infectious spreading of degradation, as described by [12,14].

Assessing the level of degradation and oxidative stability of discarded plastics is crucial for determining suitable recycling strategies. Above a certain degradation level, restabilization may become ineffective [38]. Hence, threshold values for the degradation level should be identified, enabling the definition of appropriate recycling or other valorization routes. In this study, we demonstrate that CL analysis is an analytical tool able to assess both the degradation level and oxidative stability of PP through a single and uncomplicated experiment. This study defines degradation parameters obtained from the CL analysis, which can indicate proper recycling routes for discarded polymers, contributing to the circularity of plastics.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Two commercial polypropylene homopolymers were studied: (i) PP1, with a melt flow rate (MFR) of 27 g/10 min (230 °C/2.16 kg), and PP2, with an MFR of 19 g/10 min (230 °C/2.16 kg). According to the supplier, PP2 contained a stabilization system consisting of 50/50 m. % of Irganox 1010 and Irgafos 168, at a total concentration of 500 ppm. The stabilization system of PP1 was not disclosed.

Chloroform (analytical reagent grade, Biosolve Chemicals) was used as received for the extraction of the antioxidants.

2.2. Sample preparation

2.2.1. Extrusion and reprocessing

The two polypropylenes (PP1 and PP2) were melt processed in a micro-extruder (Xplore type MC 5) at 230 °C under air using a screw speed of 100 rpm. The machine consists of a twin-screw extruder with a by-pass channel for recirculation of the molten material. Polymer granules were fed into the extruder and kept for 2 min in recirculation mode before exiting the die, followed by cooling under air at room temperature before granulation. The extruded granules were reprocessed under the same conditions up to six cycles. The samples are labelled as C0 to C6, where the integers refer to the number of (re) processing cycles (in which "0" denotes the virgin, unprocessed polymer).

2.2.2. Compression molding

Polymer granules were compression molded into films with a

Fig. 1. Auto-oxidation cycle of polymers adapted from [14]. R = polymer chain, H = most labile hydrogen atom.

thickness of ca. 250 μm in a Fontijne press under vacuum, at 230 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a pressure of 50 kN. After 3 min of compression molding, the samples were removed from the press and cooled in air at room temperature.

2.2.3. Removal of antioxidants

To remove the antioxidants (AOs) from the samples, Soxhlet extraction of the compression molded films was conducted in chloroform for at least 42 h. Afterwards, the films were dried under vacuum at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 48 h.

2.3. Characterization techniques

2.3.1. Chemiluminescence (CL) analysis

CL analyses (Tohoku Electronic Industrial, CLA-FS5 CL analyzer) were conducted under pre-dried nitrogen and air atmospheres, on disk-like samples cut from the compression molded films with a diameter of 6.5 mm. For all samples, the CL intensity was corrected by subtracting the signal from the data obtained using an empty crucible and normalized by the mass of each sample. A gate time of 10 s was used for collecting the CL signal.

CL analyses under pre-dried air (CL-air) were conducted from room temperature to 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, followed by an isothermal step at 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 150 min. Prior to the CL analyses in nitrogen (CL-N₂), the sample chamber was flushed with pre-dried nitrogen for 30 min. Thereafter, a heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ from room temperature to 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was applied, followed by an isothermal step at 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 60 min.

To study the effects of (re)processing on oxidative stability, CL experiments were performed for the virgin PPs and after each processing cycle (C0 to C6). Different parameters related to the CL-air and CL-N₂ curves were extracted and correlated to the stability and recyclability of PP1 and PP2 grades. To examine the effect of AOs on the CL signal response, the AOs were removed via Soxhlet extraction for selected samples (C0 and C1 for PP1, and C0, C1, and C2 for PP2). All these samples were also subjected to CL-air measurements, and PP2-C1 was additionally subjected to CL-N₂ measurements.

2.3.2. CL analysis in oxidative environment (CL-air)

During a CL measurement, the photons that are emitted by the sample as a consequence of an increased temperature are recorded as a function of time. A CL analysis in an oxidative environment (CL-air) results in a curve that expresses the rate of oxidation as a function of time. For a PP sample, the CL-air curve typically shows a sigmoidal

increase from a low, non-zero CL intensity to a maximum CL intensity. The nature of the CL-air curve of a virgin polymer is defined by a couple of parameters, shown in Fig. 2a: the initial CL intensity (CL_i), the oxygen induction time (CL-OIT), the maximum CL intensity (CL_{max}), the time at the maximum CL intensity (t_{max}), and the CL rate during auto-oxidation (i.e., the slope of the auto-oxidation region; R_{CL}) [27]. The CL oxidation induction time (CL-OIT) was determined from the intersection of two tangent lines, one drawn through the stable CL_i signal and the other drawn through the auto-oxidation region. The CL rate during auto-oxidation was defined as the slope of the tangent line through the part of the curve with the sigmoidal increase. A peak was observed at the beginning of the CL-air curve for reprocessed PP samples. These peaks were integrated and are referred to as total luminescence intensity in air (TLI-air). Many of these CL parameters have been successfully used in the past and can be effectively employed to assess the degradation and the stability of PP [15,26–29,31–37].

In a CL experiment in air, the oxidation rate as a function of time is reflected. The slope of the CL curve in the auto-oxidation region can be expressed as the rate of CL or as the acceleration of oxidation. We will refer to the slope of the auto-oxidation as the rate of CL (R_{CL}). The rate of CL should not be confused with the oxidation rate (R_{ox}), since the latter is expressed by the CL signal itself.

2.3.3. CL analysis in inert environment (CL-N₂)

During a CL analysis conducted in an inert environment (e.g. N₂), hydroperoxides present in PP samples are decomposed as the temperature increases, resulting in a peak in the CL graph. This peak area represents the total luminescence intensity in nitrogen (TLI-N₂), which is known to be proportional to the concentration of hydroperoxides [29]. The parameters TLI-N₂ and the temperature at the TLI peak maximum (T_{max}) were obtained from the CL-N₂ analyses, shown in Fig. 2b

2.3.4. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC measurements (TA Instruments model Q2000) were performed to measure the oxygen induction time (DSC-OIT) of the samples. The temperature was increased from room temperature to 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under a N₂ atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and kept isothermal for 5 min. Subsequently, the inert atmosphere was switched to dry air. The point at which the atmosphere switched was defined as $t = 0$. The time required to reach the exothermic peak of oxidation was taken as DSC-OIT value since it could be determined more accurately than the onset of the exothermic event.

Fig. 2. Parameters obtained from the CL analysis. (a) From the CL-air analysis: oxygen induction time (CL-OIT); maximum CL intensity (CL_{max}); time at the maximum CL intensity (t_{max}); and CL rate during auto-oxidation (R_{CL}). (b) From the CL-N₂ analysis: total luminescence intensity in nitrogen (TLI-N₂); and the temperature at the TLI peak maximum (T_{max}).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Results CL-air

Fig. 3a and 3b show the CL-air curves as a function of time for the multiple-times extruded samples PP1 and PP2, respectively. Duplicate measurements are included in the supplementary information (Figure S1 and S2 for PP1 and PP2, respectively). From Fig. 3a and 3b, the OIT, the CL rate during auto-oxidation (R_{CL}), the time at the maximum CL intensity (t_{max}), and the area of the total luminescence intensity peak (TLI-

air) were determined. These characteristics are plotted as a function of the number of processing cycles in Fig. 3c–f. The first processing cycle of PP1 results in an initial decrease of the OIT and t_{max} , and a larger R_{CL} (as observed by the steeper slope of the CL curve). Further reprocessing steps do not induce substantial modifications of these parameters. Additionally, reprocessing leads to the appearance of a peak at the very beginning of the measurement (TLI-air). The intensity of this peak increases with the number of processing cycles. The OIT and t_{max} values of PP2 also decrease with reprocessing, reaching their minimum at cycle 5. Furthermore, the R_{CL} of PP2 increases gradually up to the fifth

Fig. 3. CL-air results of C0-C3 and C5 of multiple times reprocessed PP1 (a) and PP2 (b). Parameters obtained from CL-air measurements as a function of the number of processing cycles for PP1 and PP2. (c) Oxidation induction time (CL-OIT); (d) CL rate during auto-oxidation (R_{CL} ; slope of auto-oxidation); (e) Time at the maximum CL intensity; and (f) Area of the TLI-air peak (thermal history peak).

processing cycle. Similar to PP1, an initial peak (TLI-air) appears in the CL curve of PP2, increasing the number of processing cycles; however, the area of the TLI-air peak increases faster for PP1. Also, the changes in the CL curves of PP2 occur gradually, along the consecutive processing cycles, diverging from the results of PP1.

Fig. 4a and 4b present the CL-air results of the samples PP1 and PP2, respectively, after extraction of the AOs via Soxhlet. For comparison, the CL curves of the non-extracted (stabilized) sample C1 of PP1, and samples C1, C2, and C5 of PP2 are also shown. Removing the AOs from PP1 (PP1-C0 – extracted in Fig. 4a) results in an OIT similar to that of unextracted PP1 that was processed once (PP1-C1 in Fig. 4a). For the PP2 samples, the OIT of the virgin, AO-extracted sample (PP2-C0 – extracted in Fig. 4b) is comparable to the OIT of the sample processed five times (PP2-C5 in Fig. 4b). These comparisons demonstrate that the AOs of PP2 were entirely consumed after five processing cycles, whereas it only took one processing cycle to almost deplete the AOs in PP1. It is presumed that the AO concentration is higher in virgin PP2 than in virgin PP1, since it takes up to five processing cycles to reach the minimum OIT value for PP2, whereas it only takes one processing cycle for PP1. A similar effect of the extraction of the AOs was observed on the rate of CL during auto-oxidation, demonstrating that the presence of AOs also influences the R_{CL} .

3.2. Discussion CL-air

The CL-OIT value depends on the intrinsic stability of the polymer and the effectiveness of the AOs, and is used as a measure of the oxidative stability of polymers [27]. The increase of the CL-air intensity after the OIT point captures the self-catalyzing nature of the oxidative degradation of PP. For periods longer than the OIT, it is assumed that the AOs were consumed and auto-oxidation occurs, leading to the CL-air signal increment. After reaching the time at the maximum CL intensity (t_{max}), the CL intensity either remains constant or decreases, and the sample is in a severe state of oxidation [39].

The degradation mechanisms of polyolefins, e.g. polyethylene (PE) and PP, are comparable [40]. Catalina *et al.* assessed the stability of (PE) sheets containing different stabilization systems by examining OIT and t_{max} [31]. They established that both OIT and t_{max} of a CL measurement in an oxidative atmosphere could be used to determine the efficiency of stabilizers in PE sheets, whereby a more efficient stabilizer results in higher OIT and t_{max} values [31]. These previous results agree with our findings, since we observed a decrease in t_{max} and CL-OIT (Figs. 3c and 3e) with an increasing number of processing cycles, i.e., reducing the

stability of the samples due to AO consumption.

However, the CL rates during auto-oxidation (R_{CL}) reported by Catalina *et al.* were virtually identical for all their samples [31]. It is reported that the inherent susceptibility to oxidation is the same for all studied PE sheets once all AOs were consumed, which is in contrast with our findings. From our results of the AOs-extracted PP samples, we could conclude that samples C0 – C3 of PP2 still contained active AOs after processing. Catalina's R_{CL} values were not as high as samples without AOs (PP2 extracted samples). The R_{CL} values of PP2 increased with increasing processing cycles (i.e., C0 to C3), as seen in Fig. 3d, which shows that the concentration of AOs likely influenced R_{CL} .

Notably, one may consider that there is a certain thickness above which the oxidation process is controlled by diffusion [41,42]. Due to the diffusion limitation of oxygen (DLO), the oxidation at the surface exposed to O_2 is more pronounced. Moreover, at elevated temperatures, the thickness of the oxidizing layer decreases, and the surface is even more oxidized compared to the sample's core [43]. We postulate herein that the samples thicknesses were decisive for whether or not AOs influenced the steepness of the R_{CL} . Catalina *et al.* used thinner samples than those studied in the present work (120 μm vs. ca. 250 μm). Therefore, there could have been a DLO effect within our CL measurements, wherein the AO molecules closer to the surface of the sample exposed to O_2 were consumed first. At some point, the AOs at the surface were depleted and the CL intensity during auto-oxidation increased. Simultaneously, AOs from the core and bottom of the sample could diffuse to this surface, slowing down the auto-oxidation and thereby decreasing R_{CL} . Alternatively, the core of the sample containing AOs oxidizes more slowly than the surface, which also leads to a decreased R_{CL} . Thus, not only the CL-OIT, but also the rate of auto-oxidation (R_{CL}) can be considered as an indicator for the stability of PP.

As mentioned above, upon increasing the number of processing cycles, a peak appeared at the beginning of the CL-air *versus* time curves for both PP1 and PP2 (Fig. 3a and 3b before 20 min, and Fig. 3f). The existence of this peak has been described and was assigned to the thermal history of the polymer [31,44–46], and can be defined as the total luminescence intensity peak in air (TLI-air). In the present study, the thermal history of PP1 and PP2 samples is related to the number of processing cycles. Increasing the number of processing cycles enlarged the area of the TLI-air peak. The area of the TLI-air peak increased faster with the processing cycles for PP1 than for PP2 (Fig. 3f), which correlates well with the more abrupt changes in OIT, t_{max} , and R_{CL} for PP1. Thus, the presence of the TLI-air peak and its area correlate with the polymer degradation level and are potential indicators for determining

Fig. 4. Influence of antioxidants extraction from PP1 on CL-air results, showing C0 and C1, and extracted C0 and C1 (a). Influence of antioxidants extraction from PP2 on CL-air results, showing C0, C1, C2, and C5, and extracted C0, C1, and C2 (b).

recyclability, as it is known that oxidized material can infect the degradation of virgin material. TLI-air peak will be further discussed in this study, after the comparison of the CL-air and CL-N₂ results, for clarity.

One can observe that CL_{max} is almost constant for all samples, regardless of the number of processing cycles (see Figs. 3a, 3b, 4a, and 4b). The intensity of CL depends on the number of emitted photons that are detected, which is influenced by the rate of the CL-emitting reaction, the CL emission efficiency, and the sample geometry. Regarding the sample geometry, photons emitted from the surface are more likely to be detected than photons emitted from underneath the surface. Parameters such as TLI-air and CL_{max} are a result of the CL intensity and can be compared because the samples' geometries were the same. CL_{max} is reached when auto-oxidation has spread through the entire sample and the number of emitted photons is at its highest. CL_{max} being similar for all samples implies that there is a maximum number of photons emitted, regardless of the thermal degradation history or the PP grade.

At the beginning of the CL measurement in air, the CL intensity (CL_i) is low but not zero, meaning that some oxidation is taking place. In stabilized polymers, this degradation is hindered by the presence of antioxidants. It has been shown that CL_i is influenced by the effectiveness of the AO system, with CL_i decreasing with increasing AO effectiveness [32]. It is important to point out that we were not able to use CL_i as a measure of stability since the auto-oxidation of PP1 starts even before the isothermal temperature is reached. The CL_i of virgin PP1 (PP1-C0) could not be measured due to the absence of a stable plateau at the beginning of the CL versus time curve (Fig. 3a) when the isothermal condition was achieved. Besides, both PP1 and PP2 samples show TLI-air

(thermal history peaks) at the beginning of the CL versus time curves upon reprocessing, which interferes with the accurate CL_i determination as well.

3.3. Results CL-N₂

The CL-N₂ curves as a function of temperature of the multiple extruded samples of PP1 and PP2 are shown in Figs. 5a and 5b, respectively. Duplicate measurements of PP1 are included in the Supplementary Information (Figure S3). The CL-N₂ curves were integrated to obtain TLI-N₂ values for PP1 and PP2, which are plotted as a function of processing cycles in Fig. 5c. As can be noticed in Fig. 5c, there is an increase in TLI-N₂ values upon increasing the number of processing cycles, where the increase in TLI is more intense for PP1 than for PP2. Therefore, one can conclude that the concentration of hydroperoxides in the samples increases with the number of processing cycles. The CL-OIT measurements of CL-air revealed that PP2 contains AOs up to the third processing cycle. The more gradual increase of the TLI in PP2 could be caused by the lasting presence of AOs that delay the auto-oxidation and, thus, the formation of hydroperoxides.

From the CL-N₂ curves, the temperatures at the maximum TLI values (T_{max}) were obtained, and Fig. 5d shows the change in T_{max} as a function of the processing cycles of PP1 and PP2. It can be observed that increasing the number of processing cycles leads to a decreasing trend in T_{max} . This decrease in T_{max} indicates that hydroperoxides decompose faster in more processed samples and, therefore, these samples are less stable.

To understand the effect of AOs on the CL-N₂ measurements, T_{max} of

Fig. 5. CL-N₂ results of multiple times reprocessed C0-C3 and C5 of PP1 (a) and C0-C6 of PP2 (b). TLI-N₂ as a function of the number of processing cycles for PP1 and PP2 (c); Change of T_{max} as a function of processing cycles for PP1 and PP2 in CL-N₂ (d).

the sample PP2-C1 was analyzed before and after the AO extraction procedure. The T_{max} of PP2-C1 and PP2-C1-extracted were 144 ± 2 °C and 151.2 ± 0.8 °C, respectively, indicating that the reduction in AO content increases T_{max} . Therefore, the decrease in T_{max} with the number of processing cycles, as indicated in 5d, may be related to the gradual increase in the concentration of degradation products instead of the decrease in AO concentration. It seems that the hydroperoxide decomposition is facilitated by the presence of degradation products. The T_{max} of PP2-C1-extracted is higher than that of PP2-C1, most likely due to the removal of oxidized low molecular weight compounds during Soxhlet extraction, leading to a higher stability and consequently higher T_{max} for the sample PP2-C1-extracted.

3.4. Correlation between CL-air and CL-N₂

The CL-N₂ and CL-air measurements started at room temperature, using an initial heating rate of 10 °C/min up to 180 °C (CL-air) or 200 °C (CL-N₂). In both measurements, a peak appeared during the dynamic ramp phases. The TLI-N₂ values are proportional to the hydroperoxide content formed during reprocessing. Figs. 6a and 6b present the TLI-air peaks for multiple-times extruded PP1 and PP2 samples, respectively. Similar to the TLI-N₂, the TLI-air values increase with an increasing number of processing cycles, whereby the TLI-air of PP1 shows a steeper increase compared to PP2 (Fig. 3f). Fig. 6c shows a clear linear correlation between TLI-air and TLI-N₂ for both PPs, implying that the TLI-air results can also be correlated to the hydroperoxide concentration of the samples.

It was observed that the TLI peak of PP1-C5 presents an overshoot near 160 °C (Fig. 6a), likely due to melting of the sample [26]. As PP degrades, its melting peak shifts to lower temperatures, causing an overlap between the CL emission induced by hydroperoxide

decomposition and melting in PP1-C5. Melting increases the mobility of the chains, and may expose more decomposing hydroperoxides to the surface, both leading to an increase in the reaction rate and an increase in the CL intensity. Thereafter, auto-oxidation rapidly follows once the melting has been completed. The DSC results for the first heating of the samples PP1-C0 to C5, showing the effect of the number of processing steps on melting temperature, are presented in the supplementary information (Figure S4).

Luminescence originates from excited carbonyl groups that emit a photon when they fall back to their ground state. There is no consensus about the reaction mechanism leading to the formation of these excited carbonyl groups [46,47]. The most accepted mechanism is the termination of two peroxy radicals whereby an alcohol group and an (excited) carbonyl group are formed. Following the auto-oxidation cycle shown in Fig. 1, all radicals that are formed after the hydroperoxide decomposition react further with oxygen to generate peroxy radicals. Under an inert environment, however, it is not straightforward that hydroperoxide decomposition leads to peroxy radicals since newly formed radicals cannot react with oxygen from the environment. Our results support this explanation since the TLI-air values are ca. 2 to 4 times higher than the corresponding TLI-N₂ values, indicating that more CL-emitting species are formed during the hydroperoxide decomposition in an oxidative environment compared to an inert one.

3.5. Correlation between CL-air and DSC

DSC-OIT measurements were also performed, and Fig. 7 compares the OIT values assessed by DSC and CL measurements. CL-OIT and DSC-OIT correlate well, as shown by the coefficient of determination (R^2) values close to 1. DSC-OIT displays a similar trend as the CL-OIT for both PPs, as OIT values for PP1 plummeted to a minimum value after one

Fig. 6. CL-air results of the temperature ramp at the beginning of the CL-air measurement of multiple times reprocessed C0-C3 and C5 of PP1 (a) and C0-C6 of PP2 (b). Correlation between TLI-air and TLI-N₂ for PP1 and PP2 (c).

Fig. 7. Correlation between the DSC-OIT and CL-OIT for PP1 and PP2.

cycle of processing, while OIT values for PP2 dropped to a minimum value after five processing cycles.

The CL technique to assess polymer degradation and stability has some advantages over DSC. While the DSC curve is a result of all the endo- and exothermic reactions that happen in the sample, the CL curve is related to one type of reaction [36,48]. Another even more important advantage of CL is the high sensitivity, which makes it possible to measure oxidation at lower temperatures. Below the melting temperature of the polymer, the degradation kinetics and mechanisms are different, and there are fewer effects of additive diffusion [41,48]. Additionally, the high sensitivity of CL, even at temperatures below the melting point, provides further information about the degradation level of PP through the TLI-air. Since TLI-air provides an indication of the hydroperoxide content (as shown in 3.4), the CL-air measurement can be utilized to measure both stability and hydroperoxide content of recycled PP.

3.6. CL as an indicator for recyclability

Oxidative degradation of PP during its processing and lifetime leads to a decrease in the average molecular weight, an increase in the amount of oxidation products on the polymer's backbone, and consumption of antioxidants, all negatively affecting PP's recyclability [8,14]. A decrease in molecular weight leads to a change in mechanical properties and flow characteristics. The consumption of antioxidants can lead to a decreased stability during processing and a reduction of the long-term stability during the lifetime, depending on the type of antioxidant that was consumed. The formation of an excessive amount of oxidized products during PP's lifetime, such as hydroperoxides, may further accelerate the degradation rate during melt processing, resulting in a faster consumption of the antioxidants and reduced stability [21,30]. Modelling experiments have shown that preoxidation of PP could lead to a drastic decrease of the stabilizer efficiency [38]. Therefore, it is crucial to understand the stability and the degradation level of a plastic before it is recycled so that failure due to degradation in the next stage of the life cycle can be prevented, either by restabilizing or diverting the plastic to chemical recycling pathways.

A potential new indicator for recyclability of a waste polymer should therefore include assessment of (i) the degradation level and (ii) the stability of a certain polymer, including specific thresholds. Such an indicator would identify the suitability of this polymer to be mechanically recycled, and additionally, which measures should be taken to improve the final quality. CL-air measurements can provide such an indicator, via the values of TLI-air (degradation level) and combining the values of OIT, R_{ox} , and t_{max} (oxidative stability).

TLI-air reflects the content of hydroperoxides in PP and, therefore, functions as an indicator of the degradation level in terms of the content of oxidized products. It would be relevant to define a threshold value for

this degradation level indicator, above which the hydroperoxide content is so high that the acceleration of the degradation rate during processing leads to severe chain scission and unsuitable mechanical properties. To counteract the degradation during recycling, the antioxidant concentration can be increased via restabilization, *i.e.*, the addition of new antioxidants during the melt processing step [49]. However, we hypothesize that above a certain threshold value for the hydroperoxide content, the addition of extra stabilizers can no longer prevent the acceleration of the degradation rate during processing anymore.

Additionally, a stability indicator would predict if PP is stable enough to be processed and to be used in the next lifecycle without premature failure. However, the processing stability and the long-term stability during the lifetime of PP are established differently, by different types and concentrations of antioxidants. The stability indicators, OIT, R_{ox} , and t_{max} , are mostly related to the antioxidant concentration. Complementary analyses which reveal the type of antioxidant and quantify the concentration, would be necessary to properly define the stability thresholds, and their correlation with the CL-air measurements should shed light on the value of OIT, R_{ox} , and t_{max} as stability indicators.

When dealing with the recycling of aged polymers, both the degradation level and stability are important to determine the recyclability. Combining a degradation level indicator and a stability indicator from CL-air, and additional quantitative antioxidant analyses, we propose the further development of a "recyclability indicator", resulting in a traffic-light scoring system, based on stability for the recyclability of PP.

1. Green: sufficient for mechanical recycling; no restabilization is required. The processing and long-term stability of the PP waste are high enough to withstand harsh oxidative conditions during processing and the next lifecycle. In this category, PP most likely still contains a high concentration of antioxidants and a low content of oxidation products below the degradation level threshold.
2. Orange: mechanical recycling is possible, but restabilization is required. The concentration of antioxidants should be increased to prevent severe degradation during processing and/or the next lifecycle. In this category, the oxidation product content of the PP waste is still below the degradation level threshold, and restabilization can prevent the acceleration of the degradation rate during processing.
3. Red: mechanical recycling is not recommended; alternative routes should be chosen. Here, the PP has suffered severe degradation during the previous lifecycle, which led to the consumption of most/all antioxidants and to the formation of high levels of oxidized products that lie above the degradation level threshold. During reprocessing, the degradation rate accelerates, leading to a recyclate with poor mechanical properties.

4. Conclusions and outlook

In the present study, chemiluminescence analysis is employed to assess the degradation level and oxidative stability of PP, for which indicators were defined.

CL-air measurements properly show the changes in the oxidative stability of PP with different processing conditions. As the number of processing cycles increases, the stability of PP decreases, which results in a reduction in OIT and t_{max} , and an increase in R_{CL} . Both OIT and t_{max} values depend on the presence and concentration of antioxidants.

The values of TLI and T_{max} obtained from CL-N₂ measurements are suitable indicators to monitor the degradation level of PP. TLI-N₂ reflects the degradation level as it correlates with the hydroperoxide content, which increases with the number of processing cycles. T_{max} is affected by the amount of degradation products and decreases with the formation of these products. Since TLI-air and TLI-N₂ correlate linearly, it is possible to simultaneously assess the degradation level and the thermal-oxidative stability of a given PP through a single CL-air measurement. The degradation level is reflected by the TLI-air, while the

thermal stability is reflected by the OIT, t_{max} , and R_{CL} values obtained from the isothermal section of the CL-air measurement. The latter values are largely influenced by the AO content. Although the CL-OIT correlates well with the DSC-OIT, CL-air measurements are advantageous since they also provide information about the degradation level.

This study shows that CL analysis can estimate the degradation level and oxidative stability of PP, proposing indicators for assessing the recyclability of this polymer. A degradation level above a certain limit may be catastrophic and completely hinder the mechanical recycling of the material. Therefore, assessing the oxidative stability and degradation level of a given PP is crucial to decide which recycling route is more adequate. Below a certain degradation threshold, it is advised to mechanically recycle discarded polymers, following or not a restabilization step. Alternatively, if a polymer is excessively degraded, it may be more suitable for chemical recycling. Therefore, further studies are required to define thresholds for the proposed indicators, aiming to identify the most sustainable routes to keep discarded polymers in the circular economy loop. To properly define stability thresholds from the CL analysis, it is most likely necessary to complement it with AO quantification techniques. Future work should also consider applying CL analysis to define the degradation level and stability thresholds for polymers other than PP.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Rachel Stam: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Pieter Gijsman:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Kim Ragaert:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Rudinei Fiorio:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Rachel Stam reports financial support was provided by European Union. Reports a relationship with that includes: Has patent pending to. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] J.N. Hahladakis, E. Iacovidou, An overview of the challenges and trade-offs in closing the loop of post-consumer plastic waste (PCPW): focus on recycling, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 380 (February) (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.120887>.
- [2] P. Ghisellini, C. Cialani, S. Ulgiati, A review on circular economy: the expected transition to a balanced interplay of environmental and economic systems, *J. Clean. Prod.* 114 (2016) 11–32, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.09.007>.
- [3] J.P. Lange, S.R.A. Kersten, S. De Meester, M.C.P. van Eijk, K. Ragaert, Plastic recycling stripped naked – from circular product to circular industry with recycling cascade, *Chem. Sus. Chem.* 17 (12) (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.202301320>.
- [4] K. Ragaert, C. Ragaert, K.M. Van Geem, S. Kersten, Y. Shiran, S. De Meester, Clarifying European terminology in plastics recycling, *Curr. Opin. Green. Sustain. Chem.* 44 (2023) 100871, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogsc.2023.100871>.
- [5] K. Ragaert, L. Delva, K. Van Geem, Mechanical and chemical recycling of solid plastic waste, *Waste Manage* 69 (2017) 24–58, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2017.07.044>.
- [6] Plastics Europe, "Plastics - The Facts 2022." [plasticseurope.org](https://www.plasticseurope.org).
- [7] M. Hamskog, B. Terselius, P. Gijsman, Multi-cell imaging chemiluminescence to map heterogeneous degradation of polypropylene plaques, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 82 (2) (2003) 181–186, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(03\)00182-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(03)00182-4).
- [8] P. Gijsman, Review on the thermo-oxidative degradation of polymers during processing and in service, *E-Polymers* (065) (2008) 1–34, <https://doi.org/10.1515/epoly.2008.8.1.727>.
- [9] H. Zweifel, *Stabilization of Polymeric Materials*, Springer, Berlin, Germany, 1998.
- [10] G. Ahlblad, P. Gijsman, B. Terselius, A. Jansson, K. Möller, Thermo-oxidative stability of PP waste films studied by imaging chemiluminescence, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 73 (1) (2001) 15–22, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(01\)00038-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(01)00038-6).
- [11] N.C. Billingham, Localization of oxidation in polypropylene, *Makromol. Chemie. Macromol. Symp.* 28 (1) (1989) 145–163, <https://doi.org/10.1002/masy.19890280111>.
- [12] M. Celina, G.A. George, N.C. Billingham, Physical spreading of oxidation in solid polypropylene as studied by chemiluminescence, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 42 (3) (1993) 335–344, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-3910\(93\)90229-C](https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-3910(93)90229-C).
- [13] P. Gijsman, J. Hennekens, J. Vincent, The mechanism of the low-temperature oxidation of polypropylene, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 42 (1) (1993) 95–105, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-3910\(93\)90031-D](https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-3910(93)90031-D).
- [14] P. Gijsman, R. Fiorio, Long term thermo-oxidative degradation and stabilization of polypropylene (PP) and the implications for its recyclability, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 208 (December 2022) 2023.
- [15] M. Hamskog, M. Klügel, D. Forsström, B. Terselius, P. Gijsman, The effect of base stabilization on the recyclability of polypropylene as studied by multi-cell imaging chemiluminescence and microcalorimetry, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 86 (3) (2004) 557–566, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polyimdegadstab.2004.07.004>.
- [16] P. Gijsman, A review on the mechanism of action and applicability of Hindered Amine Stabilizers, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 145 (2017) 2–10, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polyimdegadstab.2017.05.012>.
- [17] O. Cicchetti, Titanium-catalysed-inhibited autooxidation of polypropylene and of its models, *Eur. Polym. J.* 9 (26) (1973) 1205–1229.
- [18] N.S. Allen, K.O. Fatinikun, T.J. Henman, Thermal and photochemical oxidation of polypropylene, *Eur. Polym. J.* 19 (7) (1983) 551–554.
- [19] I. Blakey, B. Goss, G. George, Chemiluminescence as a probe of polymer oxidation, *Aust. J. Chem.* 59 (8) (2006) 485–498, <https://doi.org/10.1071/CH06174>.
- [20] K. Jacobson, P. Eriksson, T. Reitberger, B. Stenberg, Chemiluminescence as a tool for polyolefin oxidation studies, *Adv. Polym. Sci.* 169 (2004) 151–176, <https://doi.org/10.1007/b13522>.
- [21] A. Jansson, K. Möller, T. Gevert, Degradation of post-consumer polypropylene materials exposed to simulated recycling - Mechanical properties, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 82 (1) (2003) 37–46, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(03\)00160-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(03)00160-5).
- [22] H.M. da Costa, V.D. Ramos, M.G. de Oliveira, Degradation of polypropylene (PP) during multiple extrusions: thermal analysis, mechanical properties and analysis of variance, *Polym. Test.* 26 (5) (2007) 676–684, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polyimtesting.2007.04.003>.
- [23] S. Saikrishnan, D. Jubinville, C. Tzoganakis, T.H. Mekonnen, Thermo-mechanical degradation of polypropylene (PP) and low-density polyethylene (LDPE) blends exposed to simulated recycling, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 182 (2020) 109390, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polyimdegadstab.2020.109390>.
- [24] A.A. Mendes, A.M. Cunha, C.A. Bernardo, Study of the degradation mechanisms of polyethylene during reprocessing, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 96 (6) (2011) 1125–1133, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polyimdegadstab.2011.02.015>.
- [25] A.S.F. Santos, J.A.M. Agnelli, D.W. Trevisan, S. Manrich, Degradation and stabilization of polyolefins from municipal plastic waste during multiple extrusions under different reprocessing conditions, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 77 (3) (2002) 441–447, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(02\)00101-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(02)00101-5).
- [26] P. Gijsman, F. Verdun, The influence of polymer type, stabilizers and sample geometry on the relationship between chemiluminescence and oxygen uptake, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 74 (3) (2001) 533–542, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(01\)00190-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(01)00190-2).
- [27] M. Celina, G.A. George, A heterogeneous model for the thermal oxidation of solid polypropylene from chemiluminescence analysis, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 40 (3) (1993) 323–335, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-3910\(93\)90138-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-3910(93)90138-9).
- [28] B. Mattson, B. Stenberg, Chemiluminescence Analysis and Computed X-ray Tomography of Oxidative Degradation in Polymers, *Polym. Durab.* (1996).

- [29] N.C. Billingham, E.T.H. Then, P.J. Gijsman, Chemiluminescence from Peroxides in Polypropylene. Part I: relation of Luminescence to Peroxide Content, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 34 (1991) 263–277.
- [30] I.H. Craig, J.R. White, Mechanical properties of photo-degraded recycled photo-degraded polyolefins, *J. Mater. Sci.* 41 (3) (2006) 993–1006, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-006-6596-6>.
- [31] F. Catalina, C. Peinado, N.S. Allen, T. Corrales, Chemiluminescence of polyethylene: the comparative antioxidant effectiveness of phenolic stabilizers in low-density polyethylene, *J. Polym. Sci. Part A Polym. Chem.* 40 (19) (2002) 3312–3326, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pola.10419>.
- [32] H. Kihara, S. Hosoda, Chemiluminescence parameter for the degradation of polyolefins, *Polym. J.* 22 (9) (1990) 763–770, <https://doi.org/10.1295/polymj.22.763>.
- [33] G.E. Ashby, Oxyluminescence from polypropylene, *J. Polym. Sci.* 50 (153) (1961) 99–106, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pol.1961.1205015312>.
- [34] M.P. Schard, C.A. Russell, Oxyluminescence of polymers. II. Effect of temperature and antioxidants, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 8 (2) (1964) 997–1006, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.1964.070080235>.
- [35] M.P. Schard, C.A. Russell, B.T. Laboratories, Oxyluminescence of Polymers. I. General behaviour of polymers, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 8 (1964) 985–995.
- [36] P.K. Fearon, N. Marshall, N.C. Billingham, S.W. Bigger, Evaluation of the oxidative stability of multiextruded polypropylene as assessed by physicochemical testing and simultaneous differential scanning calorimetry-chemiluminescence, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 79 (4) (2001) 733–741, [https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-4628\(20010124\)79:4<733::AID-APP180>3.0.CO;2-I](https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-4628(20010124)79:4<733::AID-APP180>3.0.CO;2-I).
- [37] M. Hamskog, M. Klügel, D. Forsström, B. Terselius, P. Gijsman, The effect of adding virgin material or extra stabilizer on the recyclability of polypropylene as studied by multi-cell imaging chemiluminescence and microcalorimetry, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 91 (3) (2006) 429–436, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2005.02.024>.
- [38] E. Richaud, B. Fayolle, J. Verdu, Polypropylene stabilization by hindered phenols – Kinetic aspects, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 96 (1) (2011) 1–11, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2010.11.011>.
- [39] P.K. Fearon, S.W. Bigger, N.C. Billingham, DSC combined with chemiluminescence for studying polymer oxidation, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 76 (1) (2004) 75–83, <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:JTAN.0000027805.48648.c2>.
- [40] W. Camacho, S. Karlsson, Assessment of thermal and thermo-oxidative stability of multi-extruded recycled PP, HDPE and a blend thereof, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 78 (2) (2002) 385–391, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(02\)00192-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(02)00192-1).
- [41] L. Peham, G.M. Wallner, M. Grabmann, S. Beißmann, Temperature dependent degradation of phenolic stabilizers and ageing behaviour of PP-R micro-specimen, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 211 (February) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2023.110311>.
- [42] J.V.L. Audouin, V. Langlois, Review - Role of oxygen diffusion in polymer ageing: kinetic and mechanical aspects, *J. Mater. Sci.* 29 (1994) 569–583.
- [43] J.Y. Moisan, Effects of Oxygen Permeation and Stabiliser migration on polymer degradation, *Polym. Permeability*, p. Chapter 4 (1985).
- [44] L. Matisová-Rychlá, Z. Fodor, J. Rychlý, M. Iring, Decomposition of peroxides of oxidised polypropylene studied by the chemiluminescence method, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 3 (5) (1981) 371–382, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-3910\(81\)90043-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-3910(81)90043-4).
- [45] L. Matisová-Rychlá, J. Rychlý, M. Vavreková, Chemiluminescence in thermo-oxidation of polypropylene, *Eur. Polym. J.* 14 (12) (1978) 1033–1037, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-3057\(78\)90163-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-3057(78)90163-5).
- [46] L. Matisová-Rychlá, J. Rychlý, K. Slovák, Effect of the polymer type and experimental parameters on chemiluminescence curves of selected materials, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 82 (2) (2003) 173–180, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(03\)00181-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(03)00181-2).
- [47] N.C. Billingham, G.A. George, Chemiluminescence from oxidation of polypropylene: some comments on a kinetic approach, *J. Polym. Sci. Part B Polym. Phys.* 28 (3) (1990) 257–265, <https://doi.org/10.1002/polb.1990.090280301>.
- [48] V.D. Norman C Billingham, Peter Fearon, David J Whiteman, The use of CL imaging to evaluate stabilizer performance in polymers. *The Use of CL Imaging to Evaluate Stabilizer Performance in Polymers*, 1999.
- [49] R. Pfaendner, Restabilization –30 years of research for quality improvement of recycled plastics review, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 203 (July) (2022) 110082, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2022.110082>.